

Channel Count, Not Horizon Length, Drives Architectural Divergence in Multi-Horizon Urban Growth Prediction

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Abstract

Multi-horizon urban growth benchmarks show a consistent pattern: CNN Figure of Merit (FoM) falls as horizons extend; ConvLSTM’s climbs. The pattern has been attributed to architecture in every benchmark we examined. But advancing the horizon in GHSL also drops one input epoch, cutting channel count from 24 to 21, a covariate no prior study separates. We control for it over 5,698 CONUS tiles at 250 m by fixing the prediction target and trimming from the oldest end. Channel reduction accounts for 94 % of CNN’s 5yr→10yr FoM drop (delta-method 95 % CI [62 %, 100 %]; conservative bound ≥ 84 %). ConvLSTM’s gain holds, but the mechanism is positional: the most recent epoch produces $5.4\times$ the FoM response of four oldest epochs combined. Channel-equated, CNN leads at every tested horizon (FoM 0.702 ± 0.019 on the 2015 spatial holdout; 0.252 ± 0.009 on a sealed 2020 holdout).

Keywords: urban growth prediction, ConvLSTM, Figure of Merit, benchmark confound, remote sensing

1. Introduction

Architecture choice in multi-horizon urban growth prediction has real downstream cost. A continental-scale pipeline, once committed to a particular encoder, runs for years before anyone revisits the choice. The benchmark record points consistently toward ConvLSTM at longer horizons, yet every comparison in that record covaries horizon length with input channel count.

The pattern that motivates this paper appears repeatedly in the literature: CNN FoM falls as the horizon extends, ConvLSTM FoM climbs, and the gap is attributed to recurrent encoders being architecturally better suited to longer-range forecasting. But advancing the target from 5yr to 10yr in the GHSL framework (Schiavina, Melchiorri, and Pesaresi 2023; Pesaresi and Politis 2023; Freire et al. 2016) removes the most recent input epoch, the 2010 observation, and drops channel count from 24 to 21 (each epoch carries built-up fraction, building volume, and population density). Ev-

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Oral Presentation Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3–6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

ery deep-learning multi-horizon comparison we are aware of (He et al. (2025), Wang et al. (2022), Li et al. (2024)) applies this design without controlling for the channel reduction. Their reported performance profiles could reflect architecture, input volume, or both.

The isolation experiment here holds the 2015 target fixed and trims from the *oldest* end of the input stack, matching channel count to each horizon setting while retaining the 2010 observation. Channel-matched across all horizons, CNN leads throughout. A 20-tile Lagos zero-shot transfer probes the recency-anchoring mechanism in a different growth regime.

2. Data, Models, and Metric

Three GHSL R2023A layers (Schiavina, Melchiorri, and Pesaresi 2023; Pesaresi and Politis 2023; Freire et al. 2016) are model inputs at 100 m native resolution, reprojected to EPSG:5070 at 250 m and tiled into 128×128 -pixel (32×32 km) tiles at 50% overlap (5,698 tiles). The 821 tiles with `block_id mod 5 = 0` are withheld as a spatially contiguous block holdout. The 2015 BUILT-S layer is the primary target; the 2020 BUILT-S layer was downloaded *after* all training and architecture decisions were finalised and serves as a sealed temporal holdout.

SimpleCNN (74K params) concatenates the eight input epochs into a $128 \times 128 \times 24$ tensor processed by four convolutional layers (no pooling). All temporal ordering is discarded. *ConvLSTM* (481K params) (Shi et al. 2015) uses two layers with 64 hidden channels and 3×3 kernels, followed by a skip-connection decoder; MC Dropout (Gal and Ghahramani 2016) with $p=0.1$ and 20 stochastic forward passes gives $\hat{\sigma}$ at inference. *SimpleUNet* (474K params) (Ronneberger, Fischer, and Brox 2015) shares the ConvLSTM decoder, so the only axis of variation against ConvLSTM is flat-stack vs. recurrent encoding. Baselines are pixel-wise OLS linear extrapolation, *Persistence* (the 2010 layer carried forward; FoM = 0 by construction), and SLEUTH (Clarke, Hoppen, and Gaydos 1997). All neural models train with MSE loss for 25 epochs.

Why FoM, not MSE. Let G be growth pixels and $p=|G|/N$ the growth fraction. A null predictor accumulates squared error only on G . Any model predicting growth over \hat{G} adds a false-positive surcharge on $\hat{G} \cap \bar{G}$ and gains a true-positive offset bounded by p :

$$\text{MSE}_{\text{model}} = \text{MSE}_{\text{pers}} + \frac{|\hat{G} \cap \bar{G}|}{N} \mathbb{E}[\hat{y}_i^2 \mid \text{FP}] - \frac{|\hat{G} \cap G|}{N} \mathbb{E}[\hat{y}_i \Delta_i \mid \text{TP}]. \quad (1)$$

At small p the offset is bounded by p while the surcharge grows with the false-alarm rate; at $p = 0.106$ (the 2020 holdout) any model with non-trivial false alarms exceeds persistence. Persistence wins MSE on both holdouts at FoM = 0, exactly as Eq. 1 predicts. Figure of Merit (Pontius et al. 2008) is $\text{FoM} = B / (A + B + C)$, with A missed growth, B correctly predicted growth, C false alarms; it excludes true negatives, so a null predictor scores 0. We report FoM throughout with growth threshold $t=0.01$.

3. The Channel-Count Confound

Isolation design. The isolation experiment holds the prediction target at 2015 (the 5yr task) and trims epochs from the *oldest* end of the input stack, matching channel count to each multi-horizon

setting while *retaining* the 2010 observation in every variant. The 10yr-matched control retains 1980–2010 (7 epochs, 21 channels); the 20yr-matched control retains 1990–2010 (5 epochs, 15 channels). The design is conservative: SimpleCNN is sensitive to which epoch is dropped (*Section 5*), so keeping 2010 understates the channel effect.

Table 1: Channel-count decomposition of CNN multi-horizon FoM (all experiments target 2015; all-tile-pixel domain). The fixed-task column trims channels from the oldest end (retaining 2010); the multi-horizon column uses the actual horizon setting (which also drops 2010 at 10yr/20yr); the residual is the horizon-attributable term after channel count is controlled.

Horizon	Epochs	Ch	CNN 5yr, matched ch	CNN multi-horizon	Channel effect	Residual horizon
5yr	8	24	0.739	0.739	—	—
10yr	7	21	0.679	0.675	−0.060	−0.004
20yr	5	15	0.702	0.687	−0.037	−0.015

CNN: information loss, not horizon sensitivity. *Table 1* reports the decomposition. At 10yr the channel effect is -0.060 , 93.9 % of the total -0.064 drop. Propagating the two-seed $\sigma = 0.007$ through the attribution ratio via the delta method yields a 95 % CI of [62 %, 100 %]; a conservative bound that assigns all noise to the denominator gives a floor of 84 %. The channel effect is eight times the seed-to-seed spread; the residual (-0.004) sits inside σ . The 20yr column also reveals a recency property: the 15-channel control (1990–2010) at $\text{FoM} = 0.702$ *beats* the 21-channel control (1980–2010) at 0.679. Adding the 1980–1985 pair to a stack already containing 1990–2010 *reduces* FoM by 0.023. Channel count and epoch recency are separable axes.

Figure 1: Multi-horizon FoM and gap decomposition (all models target 2015). (a) FoM vs. forecast horizon: filled markers are actual multi-horizon experiments; open markers (dashed) are CNN at the fixed 5yr task with matched channel counts. Channel-matched CNN is near-flat ($\Delta = 0.004$, within seed variance); ConvLSTM genuinely improves (+0.073) then plateaus; CNN leads at every horizon. (b) Decomposition of the 5yr→10yr FoM-gap compression ($0.216 \rightarrow 0.079$): ConvLSTM improvement 53 %; CNN channel disadvantage 44 %; residual CNN horizon effect 3 %.

4. Recency Anchoring in ConvLSTM

ConvLSTM’s gain across horizons is real (*Figure 1*). FoM rises from 0.523 (5yr, 8 epochs) to 0.596 (10yr, 7 epochs) and plateaus at 0.597 (20yr, 5 epochs). The hidden state carries an accumulated trajectory encoding, not a copy of the most recent observation. Removing the 2010 epoch forces the model onto the long-run signal, which is more discriminative for FoM than any single recent snapshot.

To separate positional sensitivity from count sensitivity, we run a sequence-length ablation that removes epochs from the *oldest* end while holding the 5yr task fixed. Going from 8 to 4 input epochs changes FoM by $\Delta = +0.013$. In the multi-horizon setting, removing one most-recent epoch produced $+0.073$. The one-epoch most-recent removal yields a response $5.4\times$ larger than the four-epoch oldest removal. Under uniform epoch integration, same-count removal would be symmetric up to noise. The $5.4\times$ asymmetry fits the most-recent epoch acting as a conditioning anchor on the hidden-state trajectory. With that anchor in place the trajectory terminates at a definite spatial state; drop it, and the model falls back on the accumulated long-run signal. Old-epoch removal leaves the terminal trajectory intact because early snapshots are largely overwritten by subsequent gated updates. Activation-level analysis would be needed to separate this reading from alternative positional explanations.

5. Benchmark Results and Transfer

Table 2: Main benchmark across all models and holdouts. **Bold FoM:** highest per holdout. **Bold MSE:** lowest per holdout (Persistence), confirming Eq. 1 empirically. FoM is not directly comparable across holdouts (growth fractions 25.1 % vs. 10.6 %); \pm are two-seed half-ranges.

Model	Params	FoM 2015	MSE 2015	FoM 2020	MSE 2020
SimpleCNN	74K	0.702 ± 0.019	5.8×10^{-5}	0.252 ± 0.009	4.90×10^{-4}
U-Net	474K	0.680 ± 0.004	6.0×10^{-5}	0.229	4.30×10^{-4}
ConvLSTM	481K	0.508 ± 0.002	1.85×10^{-4}	0.156	4.84×10^{-4}
Linear	—	0.375	1.63×10^{-4}	0.053	9.40×10^{-4}
SLEUTH	4	0.056	6.27×10^{-3}	0.121	3.07×10^{-4}
Persistence	—	0.000	3.29×10^{-4}	0.000	2.40×10^{-4}

Spatial holdout (2015). CNN leads at FoM 0.702 ± 0.019 ; U-Net follows at 0.680 ± 0.004 (*Table 2*). The U-Net–ConvLSTM gap of 0.172 is the most controlled comparison available here (same decoder, near-identical parameter counts; only the encoder differs), showing the flat 24-channel stack at 250 m carries more discriminative signal than the recurrent sequence. A paired Wilcoxon test on the 821 tile pairs gives 817/821 in favour of CNN > ConvLSTM (median per-tile gap 0.137).

Sealed 2020 temporal holdout. The 2020 BUILT-S layer was withheld through every training and architecture decision. CNN achieves FoM 0.252 ± 0.009 , U-Net 0.229, ConvLSTM 0.156; the lower growth fraction (10.6 % vs. 25.1 %) compresses the FoM range. Persistence again wins MSE at FoM = 0, as Eq. 1 predicts at $p = 0.106$.

Lagos zero-shot transfer. The CONUS-trained CNN applied to 20 Lagos tiles (63,840 pixels, 69.6 % growth fraction) reaches FoM = 0.460 at $t = 0.005$, above linear extrapolation (0.430) and well above persistence (0). ConvLSTM falls to 0.228 with precision 0.673 below the predict-all-growth baseline of 0.696. Volume miscalibration applies to both networks and does not explain the gap. ConvLSTM’s hidden state encodes a CONUS-specific recency-weighted trajectory that misdirects when Lagos morphology diverges from that template; CNN’s flat-channel representation has no equivalent domain-specific state and degrades more gracefully.

6. Discussion and Conclusion

Practitioners choosing between CNN and ConvLSTM on the existing benchmark record have been comparing architectures that also differ in input volume. Equalise the inputs and CNN moves ahead at every tested horizon, with lower parameter count and 73 minutes of training against ConvLSTM’s 24 hours. The recurrent encoder closes the gap only when the most-recent epoch is absent. That is an operational fact about the input data, not an architectural advantage. Any benchmark whose horizon extension also removes input observations is implicitly covarying horizon difficulty with input volume; the channel-count control fixes the covariation at the cost of one extra training run per horizon, trimmed from the oldest end and using no new data.

Limitations. Experiments are confined to CONUS GHSL at 250 m. Channel attribution rests on three single-seed FoM values. The delta-method 95 % CI is wide ([62 %, 100 %]) and the 84 % conservative floor is a sensitivity argument, not the CI lower bound. The two-seed $\sigma = 0.007$ would tighten under at least five seeds. The channel-count isolation was performed only for SimpleCNN; whether ConvLSTM’s gain is partly channel-count-driven was not tested with the equivalent ablation. DS-ConvLSTM (He et al. 2025) is cited as the primary exemplar of the confound but not run as a baseline due to implementation availability. The 20-tile Lagos evaluation supports directional but not quantitative transfer claims.

The pattern that motivated this work, with CNN FoM falling at longer horizons and ConvLSTM FoM climbing, turns out to be largely arithmetic. A channel-count control adds one training run per horizon variant. Without it, the architectural and horizon comparisons remain confounded.

Data and code. GHSL R2023A is available from the European Commission JRC (<https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>); the benchmark and code are at <https://github.com/rohanbalixz/Multi-Horizon-Urban-Growth-Pred>. Full ablations and uncertainty analysis are reported in Bali (2026).

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